
THE ROLE OF MENTORING AND TEACHER ATTITUDES IN ENHANCING GIRL-CHILD PARTICIPATION IN CHEMISTRY

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Abstract

This study investigated how mentoring and teacher attitudes influence and enhance the participation of the girl-child in chemistry education. The study adopted a descriptive research design. The study population comprised all female students enrolled in Public Senior Secondary Schools within the Egor Local Government Area of Edo State, totalling 5,574 respondents. The instrument used for the study was a questionnaire modified from Oyakhrome (2021) with a reliability index of 0.77 using Cronbach Alpha. Multistage sampling techniques, including systematic sampling and simple random sampling, were employed to choose the study sample. Findings showed that the respondents agreed that mentoring enhances the girl-child participation in chemistry. Also, respondents agreed that the attitude of teachers enhances the girl-child participation in chemistry. For the hypotheses tested, it was discovered that there was a significant difference in the extent to which mentoring enhances the girl-child participation in chemistry based on location. There was a difference in the extent to which mentoring enhances the girl-child participation in chemistry based on location. The study emphasized how instructor attitudes and mentoring greatly increase girls' involvement in chemistry. The study concluded that girls' enthusiasm and confidence in STEM are encouraged by supportive instruction and female role models. Even though previous research indicated that parental engagement is crucial in overcoming socio-cultural barriers, respondents did not generally view it as influential. When these elements are strengthened together, girls' long-term success and engagement in chemistry can be increased. It was recommended amongst others that career days in schools should target girls, bringing in successful women across various disciplines as speakers, and counsellors should be trained to encourage girls to explore fields in which they are underrepresented.

Keywords: Mentorship, Teacher Attitudes, Girl-Child Education, STEM Participation, Gender Equity in Science.

INTRODUCTION

Chemistry is considered the foundation of industrial development and the link between technology and socioeconomic progress. Ekine and Abay (2013) argue that a country's ability to achieve good health, combat diseases, protect the environment, produce food, and develop new industries and technologies relies on the scientific knowledge and skills of its population. Access to scientific knowledge is crucial for enhancing a country's competitiveness in the global economy. Therefore, both men and women need to participate in the development of chemistry, as both genders bring diverse perspectives and strengths to the generation of scientific knowledge. In Nigeria, women have made significant strides in various fields, including business, policy-making, education, sports, and other professions, overcoming historical limitations that confined them to domestic roles. However, challenges persist, as a majority of out-of-school children are girls. The term "girl-child" refers to female individuals from birth to eighteen years of age.

However, despite the significance of Chemistry, the majority of Nigerian girls have not been adequately empowered and mobilised to contribute to national development through chemistry (Bako & Syed 2018).

Although initiatives to encourage girls in chemistry have been ongoing for decades, women remain underrepresented in this field globally. This gap is evident across all levels of education—secondary school, college, and university—as well as in professional scientific careers. Men continue to dominate the fields of science, technology, and chemistry, making up the majority of students, educators, and researchers. Evidence suggests that girls are less likely to engage in chemistry during their secondary education years compared to boys. This imbalance poses a significant barrier to achieving sustainable development, which depends on inclusive education and equal opportunities. Currently, women make up a large portion of the global adult illiterate population, and little progress has been made in improving this issue.

The level of female participation and performance in chemistry is not uniform and differs across regions. Developing countries, especially those in Sub-Saharan Africa, face greater challenges with lower levels of involvement. For meaningful industrial growth and poverty reduction, these regions require a much higher number of chemistry professionals per capita. The under-representation of females in scientific studies, especially in chemistry, has garnered significant concern from multilateral organizations such as United Nations agencies, national governments, industry, and academia in both developed and developing countries. Former UNESCO Director Koichiro Matsuura (2006) described the lack of women's representation in science, including chemistry education, as unacceptable in various aspects of societal life, stating that it is economically unacceptable due to the waste of human resources, humanly unacceptable as it hinders the participation of half the population in building the world, and intellectually unacceptable as it hampers scientific and technological research, creativity, and the prospects for peace and sustainable development (Ekine & Abay, 2013).

In general, science subjects like chemistry are often perceived with a masculine outlook by many educators, resulting in a lack of attention and representation for girls in Science, Mathematics, and Technology Education. Curricular, pedagogical practices, and classroom organisation hinder girls' access to and retention in chemistry (Fegbesan, 2010). United Nations conventions, such as the 1995 World Conference on Women in Beijing and the 1999 World Conference on Science in Budapest, called for the collection of gender data reflecting women's contributions in economic, scientific, and technological fields (UNESCO, 2014).

Some professions, such as carpentry, engineering, woodwork, mental work, and automobile engineering technology, are still seen as male-dominated, while nursing and catering professions are considered exclusive to women. Chemistry education is crucial for both men and women, as it accelerates global progress. Notwithstanding the significance of chemistry education and the prevalent negative disposition towards the profession among most women entering training institutes, it has been noted that the practical training of these individuals during their practicum is very lacking.

Schools play a crucial role in shaping girls' access to chemistry through the implementation of the curriculum in Nigeria. The attitudes and teaching approaches of teachers, influenced by their own biases, can impact the attitudes of female students who may perceive science as more important for boys than for girls (Spear, 1985). As a result, the confidence of females in their ability to study science subjects like chemistry is often disconnected from their actual abilities. Furthermore, instructional materials and resources tend to be more familiar and relatable to the experiences and interests of males than females (Udeani, 2012). This systemic discrimination arises from inherent biases that discourage female participation in critical and technical professions like chemistry. It is against this backdrop that this study strives to investigate how mentoring and teacher attitudes influence and enhance the participation of the girl-child in chemistry education.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATION FOR THE STUDY

This study is anchored on Critical Pedagogy, which investigates how teachers, as cultural workers within the educational system, are influenced by societal politics, and how this influences their interactions with students. It also emphasises the essential professional qualities that teachers in all societies must possess to effectively engage with their students. The role of teachers is of utmost importance in the teaching and learning processes of every learner. Given the significant impact they have on learners' lives, teachers must possess solid qualifications and a thorough comprehension of their subject matter and teaching methodologies. Unfortunately, this is not always the case. Geo-JaJa (2013) observed that in many developing nations, particularly in Africa, a large number of instructors lack professional competence, which adversely affects the quality of instruction in terms of both content and methods. In his work "Teachers as Cultural Workers," Freire (2005) emphasised that professionalism entails more than just having professional credentials; it involves the ability of teachers to integrate theory with practice in actual classroom settings. This implies that professional instructors must be proficient in their subject matter and well-versed in effective teaching methodologies.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aimed to investigate how mentoring and teacher attitudes influence and enhance the participation of the girl-child in chemistry education. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to:

1. examine the impact of mentoring on the participation of the girl-child in chemistry.
2. assess how teacher attitudes influence the engagement and involvement of the girl-child in chemistry education.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND HYPOTHESES

The following research questions were answered in this study:

1. How does mentoring influence the participation of the girl-child in chemistry education?

2. In what ways do teacher attitudes affect the engagement of the girl-child in chemistry?

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05, level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the extent to which mentoring enhances the girl-child participation in chemistry based on location.
2. There is no significant difference in the extent to which the attitude of teachers enhances the girl-child participation in chemistry based on location.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study employed a descriptive survey design. The study population comprised all female students enrolled in Public Senior Secondary Schools within the Egor Local Government Area of Edo State, totalling 5,574 students. The study's sample size consisted of two hundred ninety-seven (297) female students. Multistage sampling techniques, including systematic sampling and simple random sampling, were employed to choose the study sample. The systematic sampling method was employed to choose the initial school and every third school thereafter from the research population. Consequently, five schools were chosen. A simple random selection procedure utilising balloting with replacement was employed to pick 10% of the female students from each of the chosen schools. The study's instrument was modified from Oyakhirome (2021). The survey comprises four sections. Section A encompasses the demographic information of the pupils, whilst Section B was derived from Mandina, Mashingaidze, and Mafuta (2013). The demographic data of pupils includes their school's name and location. Section B was revised using a four-point Likert scale. The instrument for data collection was subjected to face and content validation by three specialists in Chemistry education and Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling. Cronbach Alpha was utilised to evaluate the internal consistency of the instrument, resulting in a reliability index of 0.77, confirming the instrument's reliability. The researcher administered the instrument with the help of three qualified research assistants who were trained. The method of direct delivery and retrieval of the instrument was employed. The data collected to address the research questions were analysed using the mean and standard deviation. The hypotheses were evaluated with an independent sample t-test.

RESULTS

Research Question 1 : How does mentoring influence the participation of the girl-child in chemistry education?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation distribution of mentoring enhancing the girl-child participation in Chemistry

S/N	Mentoring enhances the girl-child's participation in chemistry	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	Women teachers provide visible, immediate role models of educated women for girls to study chemistry	3.41	1.02
2	Increasing the proportion of female teachers teaching chemistry has a positive impact on female enrolments in chemistry	3.33	0.99
3	Mentorship can improve the self-confidence of female students in chemistry	2.56	1.33
4	Secondary school girls who enjoyed science could serve as mentors for younger girls in primary school	2.76	1.13
5	Younger girls are likely to respond positively to slightly older peers to whom they look up	2.68	1.18
Grand Mean		2.94	1.13

***Benchmark mean=2.50**

Table 1 reveals how mentoring enhances the girl-child participation in chemistry. It can be seen that the majority of the respondents agreed that women teachers provide visible, immediate role models of educated women for girls to study chemistry (mean=3.41), increasing the proportion of female teachers teaching chemistry has a positive impact on female enrolments in chemistry (mean= 3.33), mentorship can improve self-confidence of female students in chemistry (mean =2.56), secondary school girls who enjoyed science could serve as mentors for younger girls in primary school (mean = 2.76) and younger girls are likely to respond positively to slightly older peers to whom they look upto (mean= 2.68). However, a grand mean of 2.94 shows that the respondents agreed that mentoring enhances the girl-child participation in chemistry.

Research Question Two: In what ways do teacher attitudes affect the engagement of the girl-child in chemistry?

Table 2 : Attitude of teachers enhances the girl-child participation in chemistry

S/N		Mean	Standard Deviation
1	The attitude of t h e teacher makes girls dropout of school	3.10	0.83
2	Some teachers feel girls can only become secretaries, teachers or designers	3.06	1.03
3	The perception of teachers informs how they can teach and attend to the girls in classes	2.94	1.09
4	Chemistry teachers are more attentive to girls than boys in my school	2.83	1.12
5	Utilising girls' pictures in textbooks used for chemistry will improve female participation in chemistry.	2.67	1.03
Grandmean		2.92	1.02

***Benchmark mean=2.50**

Table 2 shows that the attitude of teachers enhances the girl-child participation in chemistry. It can be seen that the majority of the respondents agreed that attitude of teacher makes girls drop out of school (mean= 3.10), some teachers feel girls can only become secretaries, teachers or designers (mean= 3.06), the perception of teachers inform how they can teach and attend to the girls in classes (mean- 2.94), chemistry teachers are more attentive to girls than boy in my school (mean = 2.83) and utilizing girls picture in textbooks used for chemistry will improve female participation in chemistry (mean= 2.67). A grand mean of 2.92 shows that the respondents agreed that the attitude of teachers enhances the girl-child participation in chemistry.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the extent to which mentoring enhances the girl-child participation in chemistry based on location.

Table 3: Independent sample t-test on the difference in the extent to which mentoring enhances the girl-child participation in chemistry based on location.

	Location	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Df	t-test	Sig.
Mentoring	Urban	184	14.9565	3.37271	295	7.54	0.00
	Rural	113	11.9027	3.41207			

Table 3 shows the independent sample t-test for t h e difference in the extent to which mentoring enhances the girl-child participation in chemistry based on location. It can be observed that the degree of freedom is 295, t h e t-test value is 7.54 and t h e level of significance is 0.00, which is less than the set alpha level of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the extent to which mentoring enhances the girl-child participation in chemistry based on location, is

rejected. Thus, there is a significant difference in the extent to which mentoring enhances the girl-child participation in chemistry based on location.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the extent to which the attitude of teachers enhances the girl-child participation in chemistry based on location.

Table 4: Independent sample t-test on the difference in the extent to which the attitude of teachers enhances the girl-child participation in chemistry based on location.

	location	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Df	t-test	Sig.
Attitude	urban	184	15.1033	2.06326	295	5.33	0.00
	rural	113	13.8496	1.79891			

Table 4 shows the independent sample t-test for the difference in the extent to which the attitude of teachers enhances the girl-child participation in chemistry based on location. It can be observed that the degree of freedom is 295, the t-test value is 5.33 and level of significance is 0.00, which is less than the set alpha level of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the extent to which the attitude of teachers enhances the girl-child participation in chemistry based on location, is rejected. Thus, there is a difference in the extent to which mentoring enhances the girl-child participation in chemistry based on location.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Results revealed that the respondents agreed that mentoring enhances the girl-child participation in chemistry. This is corroborated by Danjuma (2010) who stated that female who have made their mark in STEM education should serve as mentors and role models to female students from an early stage. Such female should be invited to speak to the students on career days or other days as the need arises, as this will go a long way in encouraging the female students to study STEM and related courses. According to Khoo, as cited by Danjuma (2010), as societies open up, they often create new opportunities for women, but those opportunities are lost when they are not trained to assume such roles.

Results also showed that the respondents agreed that the attitude of teachers enhances the girl-child participation in chemistry. This finding is in line with Spear (1985), who posited that sex, attitude and teaching approach of teachers influence the attitude of female students, who they believe view science to be more important to boys than girls. In support, the confidence of females is low, such that their ability to study science subjects like chemistry is practically unconnected with their actual ability. According to Udeani (2012), school factors like instructional materials, illustrations, examples and applications presented in resource materials are more familiar in general to the experiences and interests of males than to those of females. It was deduced that the majority of the respondents disagreed that parental factors enhance the girl-child participation in chemistry. This is opposed by the study of Agboro-Eravwoke and Ochuko. (2021) who investigated strategies for improving female senior secondary school chemistry students' participation in Science, Technology and Mathematics in Delta State. The findings of the study include parental involvement, teachers, governmental involvement and elimination of socio-cultural factor as strategies will enhance female students' participation in STEM career; and is a significant difference in the mean scores of female chemistry students who agreed that parents, teachers, government and socio-cultural factor have roles to play in promoting female participation in STEM education.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that girls' enthusiasm and confidence in STEM are encouraged by supportive instruction and female role models. Even though previous research indicated that parental engagement is crucial in overcoming socio-cultural barriers, respondents did not generally view it as influential. When these elements are strengthened together, girls' long-term success and engagement in chemistry can be increased.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were advanced:

1. Career days in schools should target girls, bringing in successful women across various disciplines as speakers, and counsellors should be trained to encourage girls to explore fields in which they are underrepresented. Science fairs can actively reach out to girls, incorporating the work of female scientists and educators, and demonstrating the relevance of science to girls' lives and the importance of their participation.
2. There should be more targeted efforts need to be made to reach a broader population of girls, particularly those from poor and rural households who are most marginalized.

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